

MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES DURING PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

Jumanyozova Farida Faizulla kizi

Student of Urganch State University

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Abstract. This article covers the great importance given to the modern methods of teaching foreign languages in the process of preschool education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the modern teaching methods necessary for learning them.

Keywords: foreign language in preschool education, Finnish teaching system, sign and picture method, voice recognition and matching method, method of learning with the natural world, method of adapting one's activity to students.

СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННЫМ ЯЗЫКАМ В ДОШКОЛЬНОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ

Аннотация. В данной статье освещается большое значение, придаваемое современным методам обучения иностранным языкам в процессе дошкольного образования в Республике Узбекистан, а также современным методам обучения, необходимым для их изучения.

Ключевые слова: иностранный язык в дошкольном образовании, финская система обучения, метод знаков и изображений, метод распознавания и сопоставления голоса, метод обучения с природным миром, метод адаптации своей деятельности к учащимся.

INTRODUCTION

Today, knowledge of foreign languages is becoming one of the integral parts of professional education. This does not exclude the process of preschool education. The importance of teaching foreign languages during the education of young people has increased significantly. Natalya Kireeva, a religious scholar, candidate of historical sciences, senior teacher, said: "Either we prepare for life or for exams. We choose the first." he emphasized. Recently, he spoke about the local education system and principles, and shared his thoughts on why Finnish education is considered one of the best in the world. Nowadays, paying attention to preschool education, the social, economic and means spiritual development [interesting information in the Finnish education system]. I also want to mention that to help you succeed, we're asking preschool professionals to share their favorite early childhood teaching strategies. This list of teaching strategies for the preschool classroom provides great transition opportunities to grow and learn as a teacher.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Method of working with characters and pictures. One way to promote daily vocabulary is to have children verbally label common brands and symbols, according to Dr. Elaine Fogel Schneider, director of Touchtime International. He explains that picture-to-word translation helps with language development. That is, it greatly helps children to learn new languages quickly and easily.

RESULTS

Voice recognition and matching method. For this activity, you will need several large letters cut out of cardboard and several small, but not too large, things that begin with these letters. For example, if your letters are M and K, and you have a cat and an elephant. Begin by

telling the child the sound a cat makes. Then, encourage the child to find something that starts with the same sound and stick it to the letter. Decorated letters can be kept in the classroom or taken home to share with parents. Schneider said the activity is a favorite of the students because it gives them hands-on learning. In addition, it creates a "masterpiece".

DISCUSSION

A way to get used to the natural world. Children are very interested in learning lessons in the natural environment. Usually, a backyard garden can be a great way to educate them about the natural world. This method of growing a plant from seed to maturity is important not only for children to learn about their growth, but also for them to quickly and easily learn words in a foreign language. This method relieves stress and also helps to improve fine motor skills. The method of adapting one's activity to students. It can be easy to fall back on the teacher's manual or regular lessons you memorized in kindergarten. However, for some children, this causes problems. Gretzinger says children should be sensitive to children in non-traditional home environments. Think twice before asking students to draw pictures of their families - think about how an adopted or estranged child might feel and how other children might react. Doing inclusive activities can take a little longer, especially at the beginning of the year when you all You may not know your students, but you can tell when you're messing up that your child is embarrassed. In this, the educator should continue his creativity.

CONCLUSIONS

Pre-school education is the first stage of education and upbringing of our youth. The right preschool program should help our children grow and learn in a way that suits their unique intelligence. But children, unlike adults, do not plan the future, tomorrow. The English lesson should be conducted in the sense of "here and now". Children learn a foreign language more easily by understanding stories or winning games. If they want, they can strengthen their organ information through games with their participation. On the one hand, the content expressed in language should be related to children's life and daily life, on the other hand, activities or tasks that invite children to communicate should be interesting and important. During the lesson, students understand themselves as part of the lesson and behave and act like the characters of the play during the lesson. In elementary grades, foreign language learning is usually very effective and successful when it is organized using action methods based on life situations and games. If a foreign language is taught through play-plot situations, all children will participate willingly, because they feel that they are a part of the situation. Pupils "live" with a foreign language, primarily in small classrooms. Therefore, if it is possible to communicate in the classroom, it should be in a foreign language.

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